

Electronic Supplementary Information

Concentration-dependent photophysics of InP/ZnS quantum dots: surface still matters despite thick shells

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Figure S1. Linear dependence of the optical density (absorbance) at the first excitonic absorption peak on relative sample mass concentration for three batches: QD-G (dark cyan circles), QD-O (black triangles), and QD-R (wine diamonds). The linear scaling confirms the absence of significant aggregation or scattering effects. Dotted lines are corresponding linear fits.

Conversion of particle mass concentration to molar concentration

Calculation of ligand mass concentration.

The weight of bound ligand $m_{lig,b}$ of a single particle can be assessed as:

$$m_{lig,b} = \sigma(4\pi R^2)m_{OA} \quad (S1)$$

where σ is a packing density of oleic acid (OA) molecules, m_{OA} is a weight of an OA single molecule, R is the integrated radius of the core/shell particle.

Apparently beside bind oleates, there is a residual free ligand in the solution. We assume it's weight to be proportional to the weight of the bound ligand:

$$M_{lig,f} = f_{lig,f}M_{lig,b} = f_{lig,f}N_{QD}m_{lig,b} \quad (S2)$$

where $f_{lig,f}$ is a weight fraction of the free oleates relative to weight of the bound ligands $M_{lig,b}$, N_{QD} is the number of particles in the suspension.

The total ligand weight therefore is:

$$M_{lig,t} = M_{lig,b} + M_{lig,f} = (1 + f_{lig,f})M_{lig,b} = (1 + f_{lig,f})N_{QD}m_{lig,b} \quad (S3)$$

The total ligand weight fraction w_m^{lig} in the aliquot is:

$$\begin{aligned} w_m^{lig} &= \frac{M_{lig,t}}{M_{tot}} = \frac{M_{lig,t}}{m_{QD} + M_{lig,t}} = \frac{(1 + f_{lig,f})N_{QD}m_{lig,b}}{m_{QD}N_{QD} + (1 + f_{lig,f})N_{QD}m_{lig,b}} = \\ &= \frac{(1 + f_{lig,f})\sigma m_{OA}(4\pi R^2)}{m_{QD} + (1 + f_{lig,f})\sigma m_{OA}(4\pi R^2)} \end{aligned} \quad (S4)$$

where M_{lig} and M_{tot} are the ligand and solids content masses in the aliquot.

Particle weight m_{QD} can be estimated in a simplified way:

$$m_{QD} = \rho_{QD} \frac{4\pi}{3} R^3 \quad (S5)$$

where ρ_{QD} is the effective averaged density of the semiconductor core-shell particle.

Finally, Eq. (S4) can be expressed as:

$$w_m^{lig} = \frac{(1 + f_{lig,f})\sigma m_{OA}(4\pi R^2)}{\rho_{QD} \frac{4\pi}{3} R^3 + (1 + f_{lig,f})\sigma m_{OA}(4\pi R^2)} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{3(1 + f_{lig,f}) \sigma m_{OA}} \frac{\rho_{QD}}{R} + 1} \approx \frac{1}{kR + 1} \quad (S6)$$

where $k = \frac{1}{3(1 + f_{lig,f}) \sigma m_{OA}} \frac{\rho_{QD}}{R} \approx const.$

Finally, from Eq. (S6) it follows that

$$c_m^{lig,t} = \frac{c_m^{tot}}{kR + 1} \quad (S7)$$

where $c_m^{lig,t}$ and c_m^{tot} are the mass concentrations of ligands and integrated solids content in the solution.

Simplified estimation of particle molar concentration.

The molar concentration of particles can be assessed combining Eq. (2) and Eq. (S7):

$$c_V^{QD} = \frac{[c_m^{tot} - c_m^{lig,t}]}{\rho_{QD} \left(\frac{4}{3}\pi R^3\right) N_A} = c_m^{tot} \frac{1 - \frac{1}{kR+1}}{\rho_{QD} \left(\frac{4}{3}\pi R^3\right) N_A} = c_m^{tot} \frac{kR}{\rho_{QD} \left(\frac{4}{3}\pi R^3\right) (kR+1) N_A} = \quad (S8)$$

$$= c_m^{tot} \frac{3k}{\rho_{QD} (4\pi R^2) (kR+1) N_A} = \frac{3c_m^{tot}}{(4\pi R^2) (\rho_{QD} R + 3(1 + f_{lig,f}) \sigma m_{OA}) N_A}$$

where N_A stands for the Avogadro number.

It follows from Eq. (S8) that with the particle size growing the molar concentration steeply decreases upon the same mass concentration c_m^{tot} .

Comprehensive calculation of particle molar concentration.

A particle mass m_{QD} is a sum of masses of the core and shell and can be calculated as:

$$m_{QD} = m_{core} + m_{shell} = (\rho_{InP} - \rho_{ZnS}) V_{core} + \rho_{ZnS} V_{tot} \quad (S9)$$

and $V = \frac{1}{6}\pi D^3$ for both core and total volumes with corresponding diameters D_{core} and D_{tot} (see Table 1), respectively, $\rho_{InP} = 4.81 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ and $\rho_{ZnS} = 4.09 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ are the densities of the core and shell materials, respectively.¹

Using Eq. (S8), one can obtain:

$$c_V^{QD} = c_m^{tot} \frac{kD_{tot}}{m_{QD} (kD_{tot} + 2) N_A} = \frac{c_m^{tot} D_{tot}}{m_{QD} \left(D_{tot} + \frac{6(1 + f_{lig,f}) \sigma m_{OA}}{\rho_{QD}}\right) N_A} \quad (S10)$$

After substituting the Eq. (S9) into Eq. (S10):

$$c_V^{QD} = \frac{c_m^{tot}}{\pi [(\rho_{InP} - \rho_{ZnS}) D_{core}^3 + \rho_{ZnS} D_{tot}^3] \left[\frac{1}{6} + (1 + f_{lig,f}) \frac{\sigma M_{OA}}{N_A \rho_{QD} D_{tot}}\right] N_A} \quad (S11)$$

where $m_{OA} = \frac{M_{OA}}{N_A}$, M_{OA} is a molar mass of oleic acid molecule.

The molar mass of oleic acid molecule ($\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_2$) can be computed as:

$$M_{OA} = 18 \cdot 12.011(\text{C}) + 34 \cdot 1.0079(\text{H}) + 2 \cdot 15.999(\text{O}) = 282.46 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}} \quad (S11)$$

The typical packing density σ is for long-chain alkyl ligands is on the order² of 1–5 ligands/nm² and S_{tot} is the surface area of the shell. Here we used the value $\sigma = 3.9$ oleates per nm² (Tables S1 and S2) reported by Dunlap et al.³ specifically for oleic acid binding surface Zn sites of ZnS shell in toluene.

Tables S1 and S2 represent calculated various parameters for the studied ensembles assuming $f_{lig,f} = 0\%$ and $f_{lig,f} = 50\%$, respectively.

Table S1 Calculated parameters of QD-G, QD-O, and QD-R ensembles assuming no free ligands ($f_{lig,f} = 0\%$). The surface ligand density was taken as $\sigma = 3.9$ oleates per nm^2 , as reported by Dunlap et al.³ for oleic acid binding to Zn sites of ZnS shells in toluene.

Sample	Core \emptyset , nm	Total \emptyset , nm	Lig/QD (bound)	Lig/QD (free)	QD molarity, μM	Inorg, g L^{-1}	Bound OA, g L^{-1}	Free OA, g L^{-1}	Organic wt, %
QD-G	2.2	6.0	441	0	12.33	3.46	1.54	0.00	30.72
QD-O	2.8	7.5	689	0	6.72	3.69	1.31	0.00	26.18
QD-R	3.5	9.5	1106	0	3.50	3.91	1.09	0.00	21.88

Table S2 Calculated parameters of QD-G, QD-O, and QD-R ensembles assuming $f_{lig,f} = 50\%$. The surface ligand density was taken as $\sigma = 3.9$ oleates per nm^2 , following Dunlap et al.³

Sample	Core \emptyset , nm	Total \emptyset , nm	Lig/QD (bound)	Lig/QD (free)	QD molarity, μM	Inorg, g L^{-1}	Bound OA, g L^{-1}	Free OA, g L^{-1}	Organic wt, %
QD-G	2.2	6.0	441	221	10.69	3.00	1.33	0.67	39.94
QD-O	2.8	7.5	689	345	5.94	3.26	1.16	0.58	34.72
QD-R	3.5	9.5	1106	553	3.16	3.52	0.99	0.49	29.58

From both Tables S1 and S2 it follows that $c_V^{QD-G} / c_V^{QD-O} \approx 1.8$ and $c_V^{QD-O} / c_V^{QD-R} \approx 1.9$.

For an uncertainty estimate, we also tested $\sigma = 1.4$ oleates per nm^2 (Tables S3 and S4) reported by Kim et al.⁴ where InP/ZnS quantum dots (QDs) were dispersed in CDCl_3 solution.

Table S3 Calculated parameters of QD-G, QD-O, and QD-R ensembles assuming no free ligands ($f_{lig,f} = 0\%$). The surface ligand density was taken as $\sigma = 1.4$ oleates per nm^2 , as reported by Kim et al.⁴ for InP/ZnS QDs dispersed in CDCl_3 solution.

Sample	Core \emptyset , nm	Total \emptyset , nm	Lig/QD (bound)	Lig/QD (free)	QD molarity, μM	Inorg, g L^{-1}	Bound OA, g L^{-1}	Free OA, g L^{-1}	Organic wt, %
QD-G	2.2	6.0	158	0	15.35	4.31	0.69	0.00	13.73
QD-O	2.8	7.5	247	0	8.08	4.44	0.56	0.00	11.29
QD-R	3.5	9.5	397	0	4.07	4.54	0.46	0.00	9.13

Table S4 Calculated parameters of QD-G, QD-O, and QD-R ensembles assuming $f_{lig,f} = 50\%$. The surface ligand density was taken as $\sigma = 1.4$ oleates per nm^2 , following Kim et al.⁴

Sample	Core \emptyset , nm	Total \emptyset , nm	Lig/QD (bound)	Lig/QD (free)	QD molarity, μM	Inorg, g L^{-1}	Bound OA, g L^{-1}	Free OA, g L^{-1}	Organic wt, %
QD-G	2.2	6.0	158	79	14.37	4.04	0.64	0.32	19.27
QD-O	2.8	7.5	247	124	7.65	4.20	0.53	0.27	16.03
QD-R	3.5	9.5	397	198	3.90	4.34	0.44	0.22	13.10

From both Tables S3 and S4 it follows that $c_V^{QD-G} / c_V^{QD-O} \approx 1.9$ and $c_V^{QD-O} / c_V^{QD-R} \approx 2$.

One can see that the relative molar concentrations can be estimated with near 5% uncertainty.

Figure S2. Normalized absorption spectra of three QD batches – QD-G (dark cyan), QD-O (black), and QD-R (wine). Each spectrum is adjusted to the absorbance maximum at the first excitonic peak of QD-G (vertical dash-dotted line at ~507 nm) to facilitate comparison of spectral shape. Absorption spectral steepness which may be expressed quantitatively by a slope of a linear absorption region can serve as a hint to the degree of size distribution.⁵

Figure S3. Bright-field TEM images of the QD-G sample acquired at (a) 50k, (c) 100k, and (d) 250k magnifications, with corresponding scale bars of 100 nm, 50 nm, and 20 nm, respectively. Panel (b) shows the size distribution histogram extracted from panel (a).

Figure S4. Bright-field TEM images of the QD-O sample acquired at (a) 50k, (c) 100k, and (d) 200k magnifications, with corresponding scale bars of 100 nm, 50 nm, and 20 nm, respectively. Panel (b) shows the size distribution histogram extracted from panel (a).

Figure S5. Bright-field TEM images of the QD-R sample acquired at (a) 50k, (c) 100k, and (d) 250k magnifications, with corresponding scale bars of 100 nm, 50 nm, and 20 nm, respectively. Panel (b) shows the size distribution histogram extracted from panel (a).

Figure S6. Correlation between InP QD core diameter and the wavelength of the first absorption excitonic peak, compiled from literature data. Experimental datasets are taken from Cho et al. (brown),⁶ Xie et al. (cyan),⁷ Kuno et al. (compilation, green),⁸ Yu et al. (orange),⁹ Lee et al. (blue),¹⁰ and Fu et al. (black circles, dashed line)¹¹. One theoretical dataset (Yu et al., calculated)⁹ is included for comparison (violet). The overlaid vertical and horizontal dashed lines indicate the estimated core size ranges corresponding to the excitonic peak positions: 2.0–2.4 nm (green), 2.5–3.0 nm (orange), and 3.2–3.7 nm (red).

Figure S7. Time-resolved (TR) photoluminescence decay traces of QD-O sample at stock concentration recorded at various emission wavelengths ($\lambda_{em} = 550 - 653$ nm, as indicated).

Excitation was performed at 405 nm. All traces are normalized to their maximum intensity, with the noise background (offset) subtracted, and are plotted on a semi-logarithmic scale.

Figure S8. Emission rate (inverse of photoluminescence (PL) decay lifetime) as a function of bandgap energy for the QD-O sample at stock concentration, extracted from TR PL measurements (see Figure S4) across the emission spectrum. The lower axis indicates the emission bandgap energy (in eV), while the upper axis shows the corresponding emission wavelength. A linear fit (red line) highlights the near-linear relationship between emission rate and bandgap energy in a selected energy range.

Figure S9. Re-plot of the Figure 5 data against the relative molar concentration of QDs, c_v , obtained by converting the relative sample mass concentrations with the mass-to-mole factors listed in Tables S1–S2. Intensity-averaged PL decay lifetime (a) and absolute PL QY (b), both recorded under 405 nm excitation for QD-G (dark cyan circles), QD-O (dark yellow triangles) and QD-R (wine diamonds) batches. The open symbols reproduce QD-R and QD-G after global scaling by 0.83 and 1.63, respectively, to facilitate direct comparison with QD-O. The dashed curves are guides to the eye.

Figure S10. Intensity-averaged PL decay lifetimes of QD-O measured in three distinct spectral intervals: 510 to 580 nm (dark cyan circles), 586 to 620 nm (dark yellow squares), and 620 to 800 nm (wine triangles), plotted as a function of relative sample mass concentration. Open triangles reproduce the 510–580 nm data scaled by a factor of 1/1.38 for comparison. All traces were extracted from TR PL data using spectral filtering over the indicated intervals (shown in the inset). The inset displays the steady-state PL spectrum with shaded regions marking the integration windows used for lifetime analysis.

Figure S11. PL spectra of (a) the green-emitting batch (QD-G) and (b) the red-emitting batch (QD-R) at relative mass concentrations of 6.25% (blue), 12.5% (orange), 25% (green), 37.5% (red), 50% (purple), 75% (brown), and 100% (pink). The spectra exhibit small but systematic shifts in peak position (535–538 nm for QD-G and 643–645 nm for QD-R), attributed to reabsorption of emitted light. Experimental spectra (solid lines) are accompanied by fits (dashed lines) obtained using double lognormal functions. Yellow-shaded regions indicate the spectral windows used for fitting, and vertical dashed lines mark the fitted PL peak positions.

Figure S12. FWHM of the emission spectra as a function of relative mass concentration for (a) the green-emitting batch (QD-G) and (b) the orange-emitting batch (QD-O). Values extracted directly from the spectra (blue circles) are compared with those obtained from double lognormal fits (orange squares). Both datasets reveal a slight narrowing of the emission bands with increasing concentration.

Figure S13. Correlation between PL QY and average PL decay lifetime for the orange-emitting batch (QD-O). A strong linear relationship is observed (Pearson's $r = 0.999$), indicating that higher quantum yields are associated with longer lifetimes.

Figure S14. Radiative and non-radiative recombination rates of the orange-emitting batch (QD-O) as a function of relative mass concentration. Radiative rates (red squares) decrease approximately linearly with sample dilution, whereas non-radiative rates (blue circles) increase exponentially with dilution. Fits are shown as dashed lines (linear for radiative, exponential for non-radiative).

The decay rates were calculated from the measured PL QY (η_{QY}) and average decay lifetime (τ_{PL}) using the relations:

$$\tau_r = \frac{\tau_{PL}}{\eta_{QY}}; \tau_{nr} = \frac{\tau_{PL}}{1 - \eta_{QY}} \quad (S12)$$

Figure S15. Photographs of QD-G (green-emitting InP/ZnS QDs) incorporated into different polymer matrices at varying concentrations. (a) PMMA composites prepared with 50% and 12.5% QD solutions in toluene, alongside a pristine PMMA control. (b) PDMS composites prepared with 25% and 12.5% QD solutions, compared with pristine PDMS. Increasing QD content results in progressively stronger yellow coloration of the polymer films.

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